

The Variscan subduction record: fabric development of Malpica-Tui unit eclogites, NW Iberia

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Quantitative texture analyses of eclogites from the Malpica-Tui unit (basal allochthon, NW Spain) have been performed with HIPPO, a TimeOfFlight neutron diffractometer at Los Alamos National Laboratory (Gómez Barreiro and Martínez Catalán, 2012). Preferred orientations of omphacite and garnet are presented in order to evaluate the kinematic meaning of the linear fabric. Shape analyses of selected phases were performed with X-ray computed microtomography at ELETTRA (SYRMEP beamline) to correlate grain fabric and texture for the first time in eclogites. Kinematic and mechanical implications for the Variscan subduction system are discussed.

Gómez-Barreiro, J. Martínez Catalán, J.R., 2012. The Bazar shear zone (NW Spain): Microstructural and Time-of-Flight neutron diffraction analysis. *Journal of the Virtual Explorer, Electronic Edition*, volume 41, paper 5, doi:10.3809/jvirtex.2011.00296